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**DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONAL ECONOMY WITH MOUNTAIN RECREATION:
IN CASE UZBEKISTAN**

**РАЗВИТИЕ РЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ НА ОСНОВЕ ГОРНОГО
ТУРИЗМА: НА ПРИМЕРЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА**

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Abstract. This article explores the issues of further development of the regional economy of Uzbekistan on the basis of mountain recreation. The author revealed that the development of this industry is influenced by such factors as the specialization of the region, the economic efficiency of the services sector, the development of recreational regions, etc. During the transition to market relations in many countries, the main problem was the competitiveness of recreational resources.

Аннотация. В данной статье исследованы вопросы дальнейшего развития региональной экономики Узбекистана на основе горного туризма. Автором выявлено, что на развитие этой отрасли влияют такие факторы, как специализация региона, экономическая эффективность сектора услуг, развитие рекреационных регионов и т. д. Во время перехода к рыночным отношениям во многих странах основной проблемой было конкурентоспособность рекреационных ресурсов.

Keywords: recreation and tourism, mountain recreation, winter sports games, recreational activities, recreation, ski resorts, hotel and hotel systems.

Ключевые слова: отдых и туризм, горный отдых, зимние спортивные игры, рекреационная деятельность, отдых, горнолыжные курорты, гостиничные и гостиничные системы.

Introduction

"The rapid development of this sphere in the Republic of Uzbekistan sets itself the goal of developing social tourism for the elderly and young families, youth tourism, adolescents and children, entrepreneurial tourism, industry, agriculture, healthcare, sports, gastronomy, ethnography, ecology and education" (1). In addition, effective provides an opportunity to collect information on existing recreational resources in the area.

The rapid development of recreational activities in the Namangan region is one of the main promising areas of the economy. In the sphere of recreation, mountain recreation is of great importance. There are huge opportunities for the rapid development of the sphere in the future. On the basis of their study, it is necessary to organize the use of objects in summer-winter periods, to

identify mountain-recreational objects and their effective use. All this further increases the relevance of this study.

Analyze results

The development of recreation and tourism in the country's economy occupies an important place. One can give an example of a number of practical measures in the development of this sphere in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In December 2016, Decree No. PF-4861 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, "On measures to ensure the development of the tourism sector," was adopted on December 2. The decree sets goals for the rapid development of the tourism industry, the increase in the role of this sector, the development of private entrepreneurship and with its help solving problems associated with unemployment. "Providing tourism development aimed at identifying tourism as a strategic sector of the economy, sustainable development in the economy of the country, the effective use of the tourist Skogen capacities in the regions, improving living standards and transform into a powerful tool to improve the quality of tourism services (2).

Despite the huge tourist potential of the country, tourist infrastructure, the quality of tourist services and their level, and, in the conditions of global and rapid competition, the management system of this sphere does not meet modern international tourism standards. The contribution of tourism to the economy of the country lags behind other spheres of services and the average world rate of employment of the population" [1]. For the sustainable development of tourism, first of all, it is necessary to develop the tourism industry and recreational areas, develop the concepts of tourism and recreation and thoroughly study these activities. Recreation and tourism in many scientific works are interrelated and interdependent with each other. But the concept of recreation is broader than the concept of tourism. "Recreation" is — (from the Polish rekreacja — to rest, with the Latin recreatio — restoration) [3]. According to the scientists, the lost physical and mental forces in the process of labor activity are restored with the help of recreation. In order to restore their lost strength, people need to rest in picturesque places, mountains and foothill areas, along the banks of rivers, lakes and seas, visit historical and cultural monuments and sights. The term recreation was first introduced in the scientific literature of the 90s of the XX century in the United States, with the regulation of rest days, with the need for a meaningful summer vacation, the normalization of stresses acquired in the process of production with the help of recreation, to eliminate pressures on the neuropsychological system and elimination fatigue acquired in the process of work [2].

According to V. A. Quarterly "Recreation is the process of restoring the physical, mental and spiritual state of a person". According to recreational resources, I. V. Zorin and V. A. Kvartalnov believed that "Recreational resources are, first, a part of tourism resources, and secondly, it is an important part of historical and cultural recreational resources." In their opinion, only natural places can be considered as recreational resources. N. F. Reimers argued that "Recreation is the achievement of restoring the ability to work and health of people with the help of tourist trips or specialized recreation areas, while recreational resources are a natural climate, individual elements of relief and processes." From the above, it can be seen that, N. F. Reimers imell due to the use of a certain area of nature, recreational resources and existing historical and cultural monuments (historical and architectural monuments, ethnography, etc.). In turn, V. I. Prelovsky believed that "Recreational resources are a natural environment, as well as natural processes and individual places of nature. According to T. V. Nikolaenko, he believes that "Recreational resources are places that serve to restore a person's ability to work." It was also, and considered I. Dediu "Recreation can be regarded as a synonym for recreation." L. A. Akimov wrote that "Tourism is a different kind of recreation, one of the active type of recreation, which with the help of it is the restoration of work capacity" [6, 11, 12].

Proceeding from the above-mentioned thoughts of leading scientists and specialists, the concept of recreation is broader than the concepts of rest and tourism, recreation is considered a complex involving meaningful holding of time after work, weekly, monthly changes, as well as elimination of stresses and diseases acquired in the work process, systems that serve to restore work capacity, even recreational changes in school institutions.

In our opinion, "Recreational resources include places where a person can rest and restore their work capacity. These can be attributed to the above mentioned, picturesque places, high-altitude and foothill regions, water coasts, river banks, waterfalls, nature reserves and historical monuments, recreation places, hospitals and sanatoria, tourist bases, museums, various exhibitions, theaters, various entertainment and cultural events" [4].

In our country, namely in the Namangan region, it is necessary to develop the sphere of tourism and recreation. And for the development of this sphere, the presence of high mountain ranges in the region can serve as its basis. And this kind of sphere develops under the influence of natural landscapes and other various factors of recreation. Initially, this type of recreational activity was calculated for the summer season and mining sports complexes developed according to it. Further, these complexes developed accordingly to all seasons and even to winter sports. "To date, this species is considered a massive type of recreation. In the development of mountain recreation, the development of mountain areas up to 500 meters for hiking is proposed; in the zones with a height of 1000-2000 meters, the development of the skiing sport; and in the zones with a height of 2000-3000 meters, the development of mountaineering and skiing sports "[5]. There is an important importance of high-altitude regions. Interest in this type of recreation is high not only among European citizens, but also among the population of industrial regions, as well as people living in megacities. Mountain recreation is considered one of the best types of recreation. Its development takes place in all countries of the world. According to statistics, this species makes up 10% of the whole sphere of world tourism. Increases the population's desire for mountain areas and the seacoast. "According to the experts of the international ecotourism organization (TIES), a deep philosophical understanding of the globe, a close acquaintance with nature, familiarity with the geography and cultures of other countries, respect for the local population of regions, not the purchase of products harmful to the environment, support for protection programs environment, the use of methods protecting the environment, following the order during mountain travel are the main tasks in the development of recreation" [7].

Source: based on observations of the author and local specialists.

Picture 1. Number of arriving recreants in the village of Parda Tursun (months May, June, July and August)

Mountain

Recreation is of particular importance in recreational activities. But there are also unique risks. Namely, the descent of snow avalanches can frighten skiing vacationers with catastrophes. The organization and effective work of rescue teams, warning service that will warn of snowy weather and weather changes can positively affect the development of the sphere. In the Pap District of the Namangan region of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in a landscape mountain range, there is a village called Parda Tursun. "In this facility all conditions for summer holidays are created. But it is impossible to use this object for a year. It is necessary to organize ski resort areas. Here you can organize special ski slopes for the development of this sport as in the Alpine mountains. In addition, it is possible to organize the holding of various historical galleries, the display of new industrial goods, agricultural products, and even to show the work of fishing masters. "[12].

Source: based on observations of the author and local specialists.

Figure 2. Problems of development of mountain recreation in the village of Parda Tursun

In this facility all conditions for a good summer holiday are created. From year to year, the number of people wishing to visit these places increases again and again. Every summer season tourists from all corners of the Fergana Valley come to this region. According to figures in Figure 1, in 2013, 48 thousand people, in 2014, 60 thousand people, in 2015, 72 thousand people, and in May,

June, July and August 2016, 84 thousand people visited the area . In 2016, compared with 2013, the number of tourists increased by 36 thousand people. the main reason is that the village of Parda Tursun is very conveniently located and the availability of necessary facilities for tourism. It is necessary to create even greater conditions for more meaningful recreation for tourists.

At the same time, there are other factors and factors that negatively affect the effective development of this region, which must be eliminated. Figure 2 shows the factors and causes that affect the development of mountain recreation in the Parda Tursun village. In the village of Parda Tursun there are places in 4-5 hectares that are illegally occupied by the inhabitants of the region, this leads to the stopping of money in the treasury of the region and is a barrier to the conduct and development of entrepreneurial activity. In these places, the shortage of necessary constructed recreational facilities and hotels, as well as the low level of tourist services that do not meet international standards, does not allow for the reception of foreign tourist groups. Elimination of these problems will make it possible to soon transform the region into a highly profitable and populous tourist zone of our country.

Source: based on observations of the author and local specialists.

Figure 3. Perspective development of mountain recreation in the village of Parda Tursun.

Figure 3 shows the prospective directions for the development of mountain recreation in the village of Parda Tursun, in the future it is necessary to transform the region into a summer-winter seasonal form of recreation. In addition, it is necessary to organize ski resort areas. Here you can organize special ski slopes for the development of this sport as in the Alpine mountains. In addition, it is possible to organize the holding of various historical galleries, the display of new industrial

goods, agricultural products, and even organize shows of the work of fishing masters. You can also arrange the production of souvenirs, the production of sportswear with spa emblems. It is necessary to organize a 24-hour service system, establish a restaurant business that will provide tourists with European, Chinese, Korean and other different dishes, open night clubs and discos, bars and pubs. In addition, it is necessary to build cable cars to move tourists on tourist sites. To create such a tourist and resort center, foreign investors need help. When organizing a number of ski resorts you can attract both local and foreign tourists.

Conclusion

In addition to the Parda Tursun kishlak in the Pap District of the Namangan region, there is also a mountain landscape village Gova in Chustskoye and a village of Nanai in the Yangikurgan district has a huge potential for effective use. Here, only an approach with a new thinking is needed and it is necessary to form a high level of service at the level of world standards. This in turn will increase the inflow of foreign currency and organize a new mountain skiing complex in Namangan region capable of competing with other complexes in some regions of the republic. With the help of a new direction in the economy of the region, the possibility of increasing the supply of jobs, which is a new type of entrepreneurship, will grow. Having studied these opportunities, we see the need to organize conditions for foreign tourists. With the help of this, it is necessary to develop principles to increase the attraction of foreign tourists to the regions. "According to data for 2016 on January 1 in the People's Republic of China, the number of people has increased to 1.2 billion. And in 2016, about 450-460 thousand people predict travel abroad for tourist purposes "[12]. Their tourist trips are directed to the Republic of Korea, Thailand and the Philippines. But we note that in the Philippines and Thailand, religious extremist groups are activated, because of which the population of China doubt to go to these countries. And political stability in our country makes it possible to safely visit for tourist purposes. To improve this service it is necessary to increase the level of service, the number of high-rating hotels and hotel complexes, the frequent holding of various exhibitions of applied art and industry, the holding of national ethnographic evenings, the organization of carnivals, etc. It is also necessary to improve the training of specialists in this field in the field, which will have all the opportunities and knowledge in recreation. This will create the required conditions in the region. This requires the use of all the opportunities of the tourism industry. All these actions will further increase economic growth in the region and in the country, the incomes of the population will increase, the standard of living will rise, the level of unemployment will decrease and the new features of entrepreneurship will open up.

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